

Supplementary information (Tables, Figures and Text)

A new fossil family of aculeate wasp sheds light on early evolution of Apoidea (Hymenoptera)

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Table S1. Terminals added to Melo's (1999) dataset.

Terminal	Species	Material
<i>Pachycondyla</i>	<i>P. striata</i> Smith	DZUP material, male and queen (<i>P. striata</i>), male (<i>Fulakora</i> sp.)
† <i>Burmasphex</i>	† <i>B. mirabilis</i> sp.n.	DZUP Bur-017a, male, holotype
	† <i>B. sulcatus</i> Melo & Rosa	DZUP Bur-503, male, holotype
	† <i>B. pilosus</i> Melo & Rosa	DZUP Bur-448, male, holotype
† <i>Callisphex</i>	† <i>C. robustus</i> gen. et sp.n.	DZUP Bur-1346a, female, holotype
† <i>Decasphex</i>	† <i>D. cretacicus</i> Zheng, Zhang & Rasnitsyn	Data from Zheng <i>et al.</i> (2021), female, holotype
† <i>Simplisphex</i>	† <i>S. sutellatus</i> gen. et sp.n.	DZUP Bur-036, male, holotype. DZUP
	† <i>S. burmensis</i> gen. et sp.n.	DZUP Bur-589, male, holotype
† <i>Angarosphex myrmicopterus</i>	† <i>A. myrmicopterus</i> Rasnitsyn	PIN n°3064/629, male?, holotype
† <i>Angarosphex. alethes</i> sp.n.	† <i>Angarosphex. alethes</i> sp.n.	Studied by high resolution photos DZUP Bur-1429, male, holotype

Table S1. Partitioning scheme of the morphological data by homoplasy criterion (Rosa *et al.*, 2019) used in the Bayesian analyses. The partitions are indicated followed to each homoplasy value and their respective character sets.

Partitions	Homoplasy values	Characters
Partition 1	0.00	3, 6, 29, 38, 39, 40, 42, 43, 47, 56, 64, 69, 73, 87, 89, 90, 101, 108, 112, 118, 120, 124, 128, 134, 142.
Partition 2	0.25	7, 26, 36, 41, 48, 53, 59, 63, 72, 74, 81, 84, 111, 116, 119, 129, 136, 140, 144, 146, 147.
Partition 3	0.40	49, 52, 60, 61, 70, 92, 93, 102, 117, 122, 123, 137, 139.
Partition 4	0.50	57, 67, 75, 82, 86, 95, 110, 133.
Partition 5	0.57	22, 30, 44, 51, 77, 79, 80, 94, 105, 141.
Partition 6	0.63	1, 13, 14, 20, 23, 24, 28, 91, 100, 107, 115, 121.
Partition 7	0.67	17, 19, 25, 31, 71, 98, 113, 138.
Partition 8	0.70	2, 15, 46, 55, 62, 78, 85, 96, 145.
Partition 9	0.73	8, 10, 32, 88, 97, 114, 126, 130, 131.
Partition 10	0.75	11, 37, 68, 125, 135, 143.
Partition 11	0.77	5, 9, 27, 76.
Partition 12	0.79	12, 35, 45, 65, 99, 103, 104.
Partition 13	0.80	4, 50, 54, 83.
Partition 14	0.81	16, 58, 66, 106.
Partition 15	0.82	34, 109.
Partition 16	0.84	132.
Partition 17	0.86	33, 127.
Partition 18	0.87	18.
Partition 19	0.88	21.

Figure S1. Bayesian tree with majority rule consensus with all-compatible groups added (*Contype* = *allcompat*).

Figure S2. Bayesian tree with 50% majority rule consensus (*Contype = Halfcompat*).

Figure S3. Parsimony tree with unambiguous changes.

Figure S4. †*Burmasphex mirabilis* sp.n. (Burmasphecidae fam.n., mid-Cretaceous, Burmese amber, male holotype - DZUP Bur-017a). A, lateral habitus; B, mesosoma, lateral view; C, mesosoma, dorsal view; D, detail of head and anterior portion of mesosoma, dorsal view; E, mesosoma, ventral view; F, metasoma, ventral view. (Scale bars = A, 1mm, B-F, 0.5mm).

Figure S5. †*Burmasphex mirabilis* sp.n. (Burmasphecidae fam.n., mid-Cretaceous, Burmese amber, male holotype - DZUP Bur-017a). A, head and mesosoma, dorsal view; B, fore wing; C, hind wing; D, head, frontal view; E, posterior tarsus; F, head and mesosoma, lateral view. (Scale bars = 0.5mm).

Figure S6. †*Angarosphex alethes* sp.n. (Angarosphecidae Rasnitsyn, mid-Cretaceous, Burmese amber, male holotype - DZUP Bur-1429). A, mesosoma, lateral view; B, mesosoma, ventral view; C, hind wing; D, mesosoma, ventral view. (Scale bars = 0.5mm).

Text S1. Characters list from Melo (1999) with reinterpretations and new characters. Below we present the character list from Melo (1999) and detail the interpretation of some characters as they apply to †*Burmasphex* Melo & Rosa, †*Callisphex* **gen.n.**, †*Decasphex* Zheng, Zhang et Rasnitsyn, †*Simplisphex* **gen.n.**, †*Angarosphex* Rasnitsyn and *Pachycondyla* Smith. In the latter, queens and males differ in many features, with a strong dimorphism between them. For most characters, we coded the conditions present in the male, considering that the queen exhibits a higher degree of morphological specialization. When applicable, we discuss the differences observed in each sex. For a few characters in which *Pachycondyla* exhibits a high degree of divergence, we coded the conditions found in males of an unidentified species of *Fulakora* Mann, an ant genus of the primitive subfamily Amblyoponinae Forel. Newly proposed characters are also presented below (indicated in bold and red), following the sequence originally used by Melo (1999) to refer to the different body regions.

Head.

1. Labrum:

(0) at least one and a half times wider than long.

(1) less than one and a half times wider than long, very flat (Figs. 34 and 40 in Melo, 1999).

Labral width measured across its base. In taxa with state (0), the labral apex usually has numerous bristles, whereas in taxa with state (1) the labrum has few or no bristles. *Podalonia* has a flat, long labrum, but with several apical bristles; *Ampulex* also has an elongate and somewhat flat labrum; both were assigned state (1). In *Epyris* and *Eusapyga*, the labrum is vestigial and these taxa were assigned (?) for characters 1-3.

This study. In *Pachycondyla*, the labrum of the male is longer than broad, while in the female it is broader than long. We attributed the condition (1) based in the male.

2. Labral apex:

(0) entire and broadly rounded, or at most slightly emarginated in the middle.

(1) entire and pointed.

(2) notched in the middle (Figs. 34 and 40 in Melo, 1999).

In *Arpactophilus steindachneri* the apex has several small teeth, but the labrum is considered notched in the middle. The common condition in the genus seems to be a shallow notch in the middle and small lateral teeth.

This study. In *Pachycondyla*, the apical notch observed in both sexes is more pronounced in the queen. For this character it was coded (2).

3. A pair of rounded or oval spots on base of labrum:

(0) absent.

(1) present.

It is not known what those spots represent, but they do not seem to be some type of sensillum; in the cleared specimens, they look like areas where the dorsal and ventral surfaces of the labrum are fused, being similar to the margins of the labrum.

4. Female mandibular apex:

- (0) apical plus one dorsal subapical tooth.
- (1) apical tooth only, i.e., simple.
- (2) apical plus two or more dorsal subapical teeth.

Some groups, like *Psenulus* and some species of *Parastigmus*, have a small, more basal tooth along the inner margin that it is not taken into consideration here.

5. Male mandibular apex:

- (0) apical plus one dorsal subapical tooth.
- (1) apical tooth only.
- (2) apical plus two or more dorsal subapical teeth.

The number of teeth varies among species of *Heterogyna*. Males of *H. fantsilotra* have two subapical teeth, whereas in *H. protea* has only one tooth. *Heterogyna* is assigned both states, i.e., (0) and (2).

6. Subbasal cleft on inner edge of mandible (female):

- (0) absent.
- (1) present (Fig. 2 in Pulawski 1995).

This cleft or incision is found in several Crabroninae.

7. Outerverventral margin of mandible:

- (0) simple.
- (1) notched.

This is the same as the exteroventral notch of Bohart & Menke (1976).

8. Glossa:

- (0) less than twice as long as wide.
- (1) at least twice as long as wide.

9. Prementum:

- (0) less than three times as long as apical width.
- (1) at least three times as long as apical width.

10. Ventral surface of prementum:

- (0) continuous with lateral surfaces or separate by rounded angles.
- (1) separated from lateral surfaces by sharp angles or carinae.

The ventral surface of the prementum in *Podalonia* and *Eusapyga* is excavated longitudinally, forming a sulcus margined by two ridges; *Lindenius* has a similar condition (although the middle

part is slightly elevated). In *Diodontus* and *Passaloeocus*, the separation between ventral and lateral surfaces is quite abrupt, but there are no carinae. These are all coded as (0).

This study. The ventral surface of the prementum in *Pachycondyla* is separated from the lateral surfaces by sharp angles only along its basal portion. It was assigned state (1).

11. Basal margins of lateral arms of prementum:

(0) approximately perpendicular to ventral surface. (angle over 60°) (Figs. 10 and 11 in Melo, 1999).

(1) slanting, forming an acute angle (45° or smaller with ventral surface (Fig. 12 in Melo, 1999).

(2) lateral arms absent.

The lateral arms of the prementum are considered absent in the bees. In this group, the basal part (articulated with the prementum) of the anterior conjunctival thickenings of Michener (1944) may be homologous to the lateral arms of the prementum that became detached from the rest of the prementum. Another possibility is that the basal portion of these thickenings could have originated from a detached part of the stipes and that the lateral arms disappeared.

12. Paramandibular process:

(0) absent or very short, well separated from back of clypeus.

(1) closing at least 3/4 of mandibular socket, but not reaching back of clypeus.

(2) reaching back of clypeus, but not fused to it.

(3) fused to clypeus.

In some taxa, for example *Philanthus*, *Aphilanthops*, *Palmodes* and *Podalonia*, males and females differ in the degree of development of the paramandibular process. I chose to use the state found in females, because for most taxa only female specimens were available for complete dissection. In *Ampulex* females, the mandibular socket is closed by an extension of the gena, and not of the hypostoma. In the species dissected, the hypostoma gets close to but does not reach the clypeus. In the males, however, the mandibular socket is closed by a hypostomal process. *Ampulex* is assigned state (3).

This study. In †*Burmasphex*, it is possible to observe a paramandibular process that extends for at least three-quarters of the mandibular socket. However, it is not possible to determine if it is fused to the clypeus or not. In this case, we attributed state (2) to this taxon.

13. Posterior wall of pharynx (between arms of oral plate):

(0) not expanded.

(1) forming two bulging sacs (walls usually covered with numerous acanthae) (Figs. 29-33 in Melo, 1999).

These structures are sometimes hard to see in specimens treated in KOH, especially when the pharyngeal walls are relatively thin. For this reason, specimens preserved in fixative were dissected and examined; due to lack of suitable specimens, most of the material dissected belongs to species (or even genera) not included in the phylogenetic analyses. Fig. 31 and 33 (in Melo, 1999) show cross-sections of the pharyngeal sacs prepared from material of *Ammoplanus* preserved in fixative. The cleared specimen of *Bembecinus* has what seems to be small expansions on the pharyngeal wall, but no fixed material was available for dissection. It was scored as (?). The male of *Heterogyna fantsilotra* has a distinct expansion of the pharynx. The posterior wall of the pharynx is dilated, but does not form a pair of sacs, and is continuous with two short expansions on the upper part of the pharynx. It is assigned (1) despite these differences.

14. Upper part of pharynx (at the tip of the oral plate arms):

- (0) simple, not expanded.
- (1) forming a pair of elongate, sometimes very large and branched, diverticula (Fig. 33 in Melo, 1999).

15. Apical inflection of clypeus:

- (0) joining epistomal ridge lateral to tentorial pit (Fig. 35 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) joining at tentorial pit.
- (2) joining considerably mesal to tentorial pit (Figs. 13, 14 and 34 in Melo, 1999).

The term "apical inflection" was taken from Roig-Alsina and Michener (1993); see their paper for additional illustrations. The segment of the inflection being considered here seems to be, in most taxa, internal to the membrane that connects the base of the mandible to the inflection. In *Eremiasphecium sahelense*, the joining of the inflection at the tentorial pits seems to result from an apparent outward displacement of the tentorial pits, and not from an expansion of the inflection; it is assigned state (0). In *Philanthus*, the inflection joins a lower branch of the tentorial arm which is broadly fused to a laminar epistomal ridge. In *Entomosericus* and *Mimesa*, the apical inflection joins the epistomal ridge slightly lateral to the tentorial pits, but these taxa are coded as having state (1). The male of *Heterogyna fantsilotra* has an internal longitudinal ridge connecting each internal rim of the antennal sclerite to the apical inflection of the clypeus. This peculiar condition is not treated as equivalent to state (2) above. This taxon is assigned state (0).

16. Eye-clypeus contact:

- (0) none.
- (1) extending for the diameter of one antennal socket or less.
- (2) extending for more than the diameter of one antennal socket.

17. Subantennal sutures:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present, not connected to tentorial arms.
- (2) present, connected to tentorial arms.

Laphyragogus and *Xenosphex* have subantennal sutures, but they are assigned (?) because no internal observations were made. ~~This character applies only to taxa assigned states (0) or (1) for characters 18 or 21.~~

This study. We did not consider this character contingent to the conditions assigned for characters 18 or 21, as done by Melo (1999).

18. Distance between antennal socket and clypeus (female):

- (0) more than one half of socket diameter.
- (1) one half of socket diameter or less, but not nil.
- (2) nil.

19. Epistomal suture, between antennal sockets, in taxa wherein the antennal sockets are in contact with clypeus (female):

- (0) not above transverse median line across antennal sockets (Fig. 34 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) above transverse median line across antennal sockets, but not reaching tangent to upper rims (Fig. 13 in Melo, 1999).
- (2) extending above tangent to upper rims of antennal sockets (Fig. 14 in Melo, 1999).

This character applies only to taxa with state (2) in the preceding character.

20. Tentorial pit (female):

- (0) below or level with tangent to lower rims of antennal sockets (Fig. 13 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) above tangent to lower rims of antennal sockets (Fig. 14 in Melo, 1999).

21. Distance between antennal socket and clypeus (male):

- (0) more than one half of socket diameter.
- (1) one half of socket diameter or less, but not nil.
- (2) nil.

22. Epistomal suture, between antennal sockets, in taxa wherein the antennal sockets are in contact with clypeus (male):

- (0) not above transverse median line across antennal sockets.
- (1) above transverse median line across antennal sockets, but not reaching tangent to upper rims.
- (2) extending above tangent to upper rims of antennal sockets.

This character applies only to taxa with state (2) in the preceding character.

23. Tentorial pit (male):

- (0) below or level with tangent to lower rims of antennal sockets.
- (1) above tangent to lower rims of antennal sockets.

This study. We could not observe the tentorial pit in †*Burmasphex* and †*Simplisphex*. Considering that their clypeus is very short, we assumed that the pit is below or level with the tangent to lower rims of the antennal sockets (23:0) and is situated on the epistomal ridge (24:0).

24. Tentorial pit II:

- (0) situated on epistomal ridge.
- (1) distinctly placed above epistomal ridge.

25. Internal rim of antennal sclerite:

- (0) level with internal surface of head or projecting only slightly (Fig. 34 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) expanded toward the center and covering most of the socket (portion containing antennifer not expanded) (Fig. 35 in Melo, 1999).
- (2) expanded and forming a short, but distinct cylinder (portion containing antennifer expanded together with rest of rim) (Figs. 36 and 37 in Melo, 1999).

The term antennifer is taken from Michener (1944). In state (2), the antennifer remains at the edge of the rim.

This study. In *Pachycondyla*, there is sex dimorphism in the internal rim of the antennal sclerite. We assigned state (0) based in the male.

26. Upper portion of outer rim of antennal sclerite (new character):

- (0) level with lower portion, antennal alveolus directed forward.
- (1) distinctly projected forward in relation to lower portion, antennal alveolus directed downward.

This study. This character is being used to characterize the condition found in extant Ampulicidae, in which the antennal alveolus is directed downward, due to the expansion of its upper rim. In frontal view, less than half of the alveolus is visible. There is variation within Ampulicidae in the degree of projection and in the formation of an interantennal plate due to medial fusion of the adjacent rims. Ohl & Spahn (2010) attributed to *Aphelotoma* (as well as to *Riekefella*) the same condition of the outgroup, but in this taxon the upper portion of the antennal rim is clearly projected and the alveolus is directed downward. In *Burmasphex*, the lower portion of the frons has a relatively strong curvature, but the antennal rim is not projected dorsally. In *Notocyphus* and *Sierolomorpha*, the interantennal region is raised in relation to the remainder of the frons, a condition that causes a slight tilt in the orientation of the alveoli; despite this, they were coded as (0). In *Pachycondyla*, there is strong sex dimorphism, with the male exhibiting the alveoli slightly directed downward, while the queen exhibits a condition similar to that in Ampulicidae, in which the antennae move up and down laterally. It was coded (0) based on the male condition.

27. Pedicel attachment:

- (0) basically centric.
- (1) eccentric (Figs. 38 and 39 in Melo, 1999).

28. Socket on apex of scape with an eccentric pedicel:

- (0) entirely membranous.
- (1) sclerotized in the center (Fig. 38 in Melo, 1999).

This character applies only to taxa with state (1) for the preceding character.

29. Sexual dimorphism in number of antennomeres:

- (0) none.
- (1) male with 13 and female with 12 antennomeres.

This study. The males of †*Burmasphex* and †*Simplisphex* **gen.n.** have 13 antennomeres and we are assuming that their females, when known, will exhibit 12 articles, as found in other Aculeata s.str. In †*Decasphex* we assumed that the holotype has 12 antennomeres, see discussion in the main text.

30. Female 2nd flagellomere:

- (0) at least 3X longer than pedicel.
- (1) less than 2X longer than pedicel.

This character is used to characterize the relative length of the antenna. The female of *Heterogyna protea* has an unusually long pedicel; it is assigned state (0) despite the fact that its 2nd flagellomere is not 3x longer than the pedicel.

31. Facets of compound eyes (female):

- (0) approximately uniform in size.
- (1) frontal facets much larger than remaining ones.

32. Facets of compound eyes (male):

- (0) more or less uniform in size.
- (1) frontal facets much larger than remaining ones (Fig. 39 in Melo, 1999).

33. Inner orbits of compound eyes (female):

- (0) straight or slightly concave, more or less parallel.
- (1) concave, diverging below.
- (2) more or less straight, diverging below.
- (3) convex, diverging below.
- (4) sinuate (upper portion concave, lower portion convex), strongly converging below.
- (5) straight, converging below.
- (6) concave, converging below.

34. Integument of paraocular area of female:

- (0) not differentiated from more median part of frons.
- (1) with a specialized area, sometimes very distinct and forming a fovea (Figs. 40-43 in Melo, 1999).

This specialized area represents the surface for release of the secretions of an underlying epidermal gland [see Schuberth and Schonitzer (1993)]. It differs considerably in development and position among the various taxa; I consider all different forms as homologous.

35. Preoccipital carina:

- (0) complete (Fig. 44 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) interrupted ventrally.
- (2) interrupted ventrally but reaching hypostomal carina.
- (3) interrupted dorsally.
- (4) completely absent.

This is the same as occipital carina of Bohart and Menke (1976). The species of *Dolichurus* dissected does not have a preoccipital carina, but it is assigned state (1) based on a female of *D. corniculus*.

36. Periforaminal depression:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present (Fig. 44 in Melo, 1999).

This character concerns a distinct depression on the occipital region. It is usually more developed dorsally, as well as laterally, and in some taxa, it is marked dorsally and laterally by a marginal sulcus and/ or carina. The anterior dorsal portion of the pronotum seems to fit in this depression; in the taxa with a well-developed marginal sulcus, one could imagine that head and pronotum are locked together when the anterior dorsal margin of the pronotum is inside the marginal sulcus. In *Entomosericus*, the depression is weakly indicated, but this taxon is considered as having state (1).

Mesosoma.**37. Cervical sclerite:**

- (0) absent.
- (1) present.

38. Posterolateral angle of pronotum:

- (0) evenly rounded (or modified differently from state 1).
- (1) reduced dorsally above and anterior to differentiated spiracular operculum.

This character corresponds to character 35 of Brothers and Carpenter (1993).

This study. This character corresponds to character 21 of Brothers (1975) and 35 of Brothers & Carpenter (1993). It represents a synapomorphy for Apoidea in relation to the differentiation of a pronotal lobe. The region of contact between the dorsal portion of the pronotum and the mesoscutum in Apoidea is quite complex and involves a series of specialized modifications. †Burmasphecidae **fam.n.** have a condition similar to the remaining Apoidea, with a reduction of the posterior margin of the pronotum adjacent to the pronotal lobe and exposing the lateral portions of the mesoscutum externally to the notauli. The pronotal lobe of †Burmasphecidae **fam.n.** is small compared to that found in other Apoidea. Considering the typical apoid pronotum observed in †*Angarosphex*, we assumed that it possesses a pronotal lobe.

39. Posterior margin of the dorsal portion of the pronotum (new character):

- (0) level with adjacent anterior portion;
- (1) slanted down and in a distinct plane compared to the adjacent anterior portion of the pronotum.

This study. This character is being used to differentiate the Apoidea, exclusive of †*Burmasphex* and †*Simplisphex*, for their specialized articulation in the region between the dorsal portion of the pronotum and the mesoscutum. Their pronotum has its posterior margin slanted down toward the mesoscutum and at the same time the anterior border of the mesoscutum has a step along its entire extension in which the margin of the pronotum fits in. Therefore, the contact zone between the posterior margin of the pronotum and the anterior border of the mesoscutum is rigidly articulated. In †Burmasphecidae **fam.n.** the posterior margin is not slanted down and extends over the anterior margin of the mesoscutum, a condition reminiscent of that found in Pompilidae, Sierolomorphidae, Sapygidae and most Chrysoidea. In Formicidae the posterior margin is also not slanted down, but similarly to Apoidea exclusive of ††Burmasphecidae **fam.n.** it fits in a sulcus along the anterior margin of the mesoscutum. According to Brothers (1975; character 19), the condition of Formicidae is also present in Scoliidae, Vespidae and Bradynobaenidae. Despite its fragmented condition, the type species of †*Angarosphex* has a typical apoid pronotum. It is clear from the photographs of the type specimen that its pronotum has a long and high collar, margined posteriorly by a narrow articulating step. Likewise, the mesoscutum, ahead of the notauli, has a depressed margin along its anterior portion, indicating that the pronotum would fit on it.

40. Shape of lateral portion of pronotum (new character):

- (0) uniformly convex, without constriction.
- (1) exhibiting a distinct constriction between the anterior and posterior portions of the pronotum.

This study. We introduced this character for a specialized condition exhibited by the Apoidea, inclusive of †*Angarosphex* and †Burmasphecidae **fam.n.**, in which the lateral portions of the pronotum are compressed and form an evident constriction or strangulation, as seen in dorsal view, right anteriorly to the pronotal lobes. The condition of †*Angarosphex* has been assumed based on the overall shape of its pronotum.

41. Shape of the pronotal collar (new character):

- (0) high and relatively short.
- (1) high and long, forming a conspicuous rectangular surface.
- (2) posterior portion of pronotum lacking a pronotal collar.

This study. This character applies only to the Apoidea possessing a specialized articulation in the region between the dorsal portion of the pronotum and the mesoscutum (state 1 for character 37A). †*Angarosphex* has clearly a high and relatively short pronotal collar. We coded it as (1). The shape of the pronotal collar varies between females and males of *Heterogyna*, being short in the males and very long in females. We coded it as (1). In *Bembecinus*, the pronotal collar is very narrow and closely appressed to the mesoscutum. Despite this, we coded as (0).

42. Ventral angle of pronotum:

(0) scarcely exceeding base of procoxa.

(1) greatly produced mesad and closely approaching its counterpart midventrally.

This character is being used to indicate the distinct condition found in all Apoidea, irrespective of the small variation found among them in how closely the two ventral halves of the pronotum approach each other. Brothers and Carpenter's (1993) assignment of a distinct state to bees is unjustified, since a similar condition to that found in bees is present in several other Apoidea.

This study. As far as we can observe, the ventral angles of the pronotum in †Burmasphecidae **fam.n.** extend at least to the posterior surface of the fore coxae. In †*Burmasphex* and †*Callisphex* **gen.n.**, it is possible to see that they do not extend further from this point and do not meet each other ventrally behind the coxae. We assigned state (0) to †Burmasphecidae **fam.n.** In *Pachycondyla* there is a strong dimorphism, with the female exhibiting prolonged ventral angles but which do not meet each other ventrally. It was assigned state (0) based in the male condition.

43. Articulation in the anterior margin of the mesepisternum (mesepisternal clip):

(0) absent

(1) present

This study. This new character was created to describe a specialized articulation in the anterior margin of the mesepisternum, referred here as the mesepisternal clip. The clip projects over the posterior margin of the pronotum ventrally under the pronotal lobe (Fig. S7). This articulation seems to be related to the limitation of movement of the pronotum, acting as an additional lock for this sclerite. This condition is found in all Apoidea except †Burmasphecidae **fam.n.** Although the shape of this clip is quite variable in different lineages, our hypothesis is that this articulation appeared only once and is homologous throughout the entire clade.

Figure S7. Anterior portion of mesosoma of female of *Ammoplanus* sp. (cfr. *apache*), ventral view (legs removed, except for left mid coxa). mc= mesepisternal clip; pl= pronotal lobe. Modified from Melo (1999).

44. Pronotal collar:

- (0) anterior edge rounded, or a collar not differentiated from anterior portion of pronotum.
- (1) delimited anteriorly by a transverse carina (sometimes interrupted in the middle) (Fig. 45 in Melo, 1999).
- (2) delimited by a carina only laterally.

45. Pronotum (internally):

- (0) without lateral ridges.
- (1) with a pair of lateral, oblique ridges (converging anteriorly).

Ammoplanus and *Hesperapis* have only a pair of weak carinae (very short in *Hesperapis*); both are coded as (1). In some taxa, e.g., *Astata*, *Ctenocolletes* and *Stangeella*, the ridges are continuous in the middle. The male of *Aphelotoma rufiventris* has no ridges, but the female of *A. nigricula* has a distinct external sulcus in the place where the ridge is situated; this taxon is assigned state (1). *Laphyragogus* and *Xenosphex* are also assigned (1) based only on external examination (presence of a sulcus in *Xenosphex* and a line in *Laphyragogus*).

This study. It is possible to observe a lateral line in the pronotum of †*Burmasphex* along the region where the oblique inner ridge is present in other Apoidea, while in †*Simplisphex* **gen.n.** the visibility of this region is poor. As in *Xenosphex* and *Laphyragogus*, we attributed state (1) to †*Burmasphex* based only on external examination.

46. Outer ventral posterior corner of pro thoracic episternum:

- (0) not differentiated from rest of episternum.
- (1) more or less protuberant in lateral view, lateral carina of episternum not differentiated.
- (2) as (1), but lateral carina of episternum, above the protuberance, forming a distinct lamella.

47. Short sulcus dorsal to outer ventral posterior corner of prothoracic episternum:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present (Fig. 47 in Melo, 1999).

A correspondingly short segment of the anterior margin of the pronotum fits inside this sulcus, although it does not show any particular modification in relation to the remainder of the anterior margin. This sulcus is present only in *Heliocausus* and *Ochleroptera*.

48. Prothoracic basisternum:

- (0) lateral segments of posterior edge oblique, converging in the middle.
- (1) posterior edge basically straight, except for small medial projection, lateral corners pointed.
- (2) as (1), but lateral corners rounded (basisternum very small).

This structure shows considerable variation among the taxa examined, making difficult the delimitation of discrete characters and states. This character is used to recognize what seems to be a distinct morphology found in the Bembicinae examined.

49. Medial portion of prothoracic basisternum:

(0) at same level as rest of basisternum, strongly pointed posteriorly (Fig. 46 in Melo, 1999).

(1) declivous in relation to anterior portion (sometimes only slightly), rounded or weakly pointed posteriorly.

The comment for character 43 also applies here; however, the present character is being used to represent the distinct posterior reduction of the medial portion of the basisternum in Apidae s.l. and Crabronidae in relation to the other Apoidea. In *Clystopsenella* and *Eusapyga*, the medial portion is not strongly pointed, but they are assigned state (0).

This study. The basisterna of †*Burmasphex*, †*Callisphex* **gen.n.** and †*Simplisphex* **gen.n.** remind the condition found in Apidae and Crabronidae, and not that exhibited by Ampulicidae, Heterogynaidae and Sphecidae. Therefore, they were coded state (1) for this character.

50. Apophyseal arms of prothoracic endosternum:

(0) separate (Figs. 48 and 49 in Melo, 1999).

(1) fused (forming a bridge) (Fig. 50 in Melo, 1999)

51. Bases of apophyseal arms of prothoracic endosternum (internally):

(0) not connected by divergent plates (Fig. 48 in Melo, 1999).

(1) connected by two continuous, divergent plates originating at base of furcasternum (broadening dorsally) (Fig. 49 in Melo, 1999).

In *Palarus*, these plates are very broad and close half of the coxal cavity. In *Didineis* and *Ochleroptera*, the plates are apparently absent, but I assume that the plates fused completely to the furcasternum (the medial line in the furcasternum is absent, contrary to what occurs in groups where the plates are originally absent).

52. Internal divergent plates of prothoracic endosternum:

(0) separate from furcasternum by a medial ridge.

(1) partially (dorsally) or completely fused to furcasternum, medial ridge absent at least dorsally (Fig. 50 in Melo, 1999)

This character applies only to taxa with state (1) for the preceding character.

53. Fore basitarsus:

(0) apex not modified, or only with a short apical lobe.

(1) with a distinct apical lobe, extending at least to half the length of second tarsomere.

The condition described in state (1) is found only in females of *Laphyragogus* and in most species of *Eremiasphecium* [see Figs. 118-123 in Marshakov (1976)].

54. Foretarsal rake (females):

(0) absent.

(1) present, bristles longer than diameter of basitarsus.

(2) present, bristles as long as or shorter than diameter of basi tarsus.

55. Socket of foreleg spur:

(0) broadly connected to basitarsal socket.

(1) narrowly connected to basitarsal socket and away from tibial apex.

(2) as (1) or even farther from tibial apex and, and spur socket almost or completely closed (Fig. 51).

In *Lyroda* and *Laphyragogus*, the spur socket is somewhat closed, but it is situated near the tibial apex. Both taxa are coded (0).

56. Leg form of female:

- (0) all similar, slender and generalized (or modified differently from state 1).
- (1) all femora inflated and fusiform although midfemur often less so; tibiae and tarsi fairly slender.

57. Claws:

- (0) with a subapical or at least one subbasal tooth.
- (1) simple, without subapical or subbasal teeth.

58. Notauli:

- ~~(0) indicated externally by a sulcus and internally by a ridge.~~
- ~~(1) indicated externally by a line and internally by a ridge.~~
- ~~(2) indicated only externally by a sulcus.~~
- ~~(3) vestigial.~~
- ~~(4) no indication (absent).~~

Laphyragogus and *Xenosphex* are assigned (1) based on external examination only.

- (0) present, complete, extending to transcutal articulation or almost so.
- (1) present, short, restricted to anterior half of mesoscutum.
- (2) vestigial, very short and usually hidden by the posterior margin of pronotum.
- (3) absent.

This study. This character was modified from the character 53 of Melo (1999) in order to separate the external condition of the notauli from presence of an internal ridge. In *Pachycondyla*, there is considerably sex dimorphism, with no indication of notauli in the female, while the male has a pair of shallow sulci anteriorly that converge posteriorly into a single medial sulcus. We attributed state (0) to Formicidae based on the male condition.

59. Notauli II (new character):

- (0) indicated as a sulcus, varying from shallow and narrow to relatively deep and broad.
- (1) indicated as a thin line, level with remainder of mesoscutum surface.

This character is contingent and applies only to terminals attributed states (0) and (1) for character 57.

This study. This character is being used to represent the external condition of the notauli.

60. Notauli trajectory (new character):

- (0) converging posteriorly (distance between notauli anteriorly at least 2x longer than posterior distance).
- (1) parallel or subparallel.

This character is contingent and applies only to terminals attributed states (0) and (1) for character 53.

This study. Formicidae exhibits a strong convergence of the notauli posteriorly, resulting in their fusion before reaching the transcutal articulation. This seems to be a synapomorphy for Formicidae.

61. Supra-alar carina:

(0) absent or if present, not meeting tegular ridge (preaxilla open anteriorly; Fig. 25 in Melo, 1999).

(1) curving down anteriorly and fused to the anterior segment of the tegular ridge (preaxilla closed off anteriorly; Fig. 26 in Melo, 1999).

The terms supra-alar carina and tegular ridge were taken from Michener (1944). This carina has also been named scutal flange by Menke (1988).

62. Setal patch on anterior segment of tegular ridge:

(0) present.

(1) absent.

This setal patch seems to be a proprioceptor field and is present in all aculeate outgroup taxa I studied. It is absent from a braconid, evaniid, trigonalid and a xiphydriid examined. Judging from Ronquist and Nordlander (1989), it is also apparently absent from Ibalidae. This might be a synapomorphy for Aculeata.

63. Oblique scutal carina:

(0) absent.

(1) present.

64. Prepectus:

(0) not immovably fused to the mesepisternum.

(1) immovably fused to mesepisternum, suture between them not obliterated.

(2) as (1), but suture completely obliterated.

I recognized only three states for the taxa included here, taking into consideration only the degree of fusion to the mesepisternum. Brothers (1975) assumed that the prepectus in Apoidea extended completely across the anterior margin of the mesepisternum, being fused in the midline, as well as fused to and forming the depressed anterior margin of the mesepisternum. Considering the condition in basal Chrysoidea and Vespoidea, an alternative interpretation for the Apoidea would be a prepectus not contiguous medially and fused to the mesepisternum only along its dorsal half; the depressed anterior margin of the mesepisternum would be a modification of the mesepisternum itself in response to a modified pronotum ventral angles greatly produced mesad). The prepectus in *Rhopalosoma* is very narrow, but it has a distinct fovea also present in *Eusapyga* and *Sierolomorpha*.

65. Mesepisternal ridge:

(0) complete, reaching anterior edge of mesepisternum away from body's midline.

(1) complete, reaching body's midline ventrally.

(2) reaching ventral portion of mesepisternum, but absent from middle of mesepisternum.

(3) restricted to ventral portion of mesepisternum (absent laterally).

(4) restricted to lateral portion of mesepisternum (absent ventrally).

(5) absent.

This is an internal ridge present laterally and/ or ventrally on the mesepisternum (Fig. 52 in Melo, 1999). In most cases it is marked externally by a sulcus (see next character). In *Dinetus* and *Lyroda*, the ridge is interrupted ventrally and only a small segment is present along the anterior edge of the mesepisternum; both taxa are coded as (0). In *Bembecinus*, the mesepisternal ridge is vestigial since only a very short segment is present below the subalar fossa; however, it is still coded (4).

This study. There is no indication of a mesepisternal sulcus or of a ridge in †Burmasphecidae **fam.n.**, which then received state (5). *Pachycondyla* possesses a transverse sulcus on the lateral portion of the mesepisternum, but compared to the condition found in Sphecidae, Crabronidae and Apidae, it has a different trajectory, crossing the sclerite more or less longitudinally and passing through the scrobe. Therefore, it is not considered homologous to the mesepisternal sulcus of Apoidea and *Pachycondyla* received state (5) for this character.

66. Mesepisternal sulcus:

- (0) complete, reaching anterior edge of mesepisternum away from body's midline.
- (1) complete, reaching body's midline ventrally (Fig. 53 in Melo, 1999).
- (2) restricted to ventral portion of mesepisternum (absent laterally).
- (3) restricted to lateral portion of mesepisternum (absent ventrally).
- (4) absent.

Sometimes the sulcus is only weakly indicated ventrally. In *Ctenocolletes*, the sulcus is only weakly indicated on the upper part of the mesepisternum; it is assigned (3).

67. Omaular sulcus:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present (Fig. 54).

68. Omaular carina:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present.

This carina corresponds to the "omaulus" of Bohart and Menke (1976). Omaulus here is used to designate the area of the mesepisternum where its anterior and lateral surfaces meet. When both a carina and a sulcus are present, the carina is always anterior to the sulcus (Fig. 54 in Melo, 1999).

69. Mesepisternum and metepisternum:

- (0) not fused.
- (1) fused, suture mostly obliterated.

66. Interfureal muscle:

- ~~(0) present.~~
- ~~(1) absent.~~

~~Absence of this muscle is considered a synapomorphy for Apoidea by Heraty et al. (1994). Only a male of *Sierolomorpha canadensis* and of *Dolichurus* sp. were examined using the technique described by these authors. The remaining taxa were assumed to have the ground plan condition postulated by Heraty et al. (1994). The loss of this muscle is probably correlated with the ventral fusion of the meso- and meta thoraces in Apoidea (condition not used here as an independent character).~~

This study. Differently from Melo (1999), this character is being used here to represent the ventrolateral fusion of the mesepisternum with the metepisternum, and not the absence of the interfurcal muscle. He argued that the fusion of these two segments ventrolaterally probably led to the loss of the interfurcal muscle, a synapomorphy of Apoidea documented by Heraty et al. (1994). Here we also did not use Melo's character 66 due to difficulties in determining the degree of fusion along the pleural suture. In †*Burmasphex* †*Callisphex* **gen.n.** and †*Simplisphex* **gen.n.**, the fusion between the sclerites cannot be directly examined. One could assume that the sclerites are not fused in †*Burmasphex* considering the small notch present right above the mid coxae at the limit between the mese- and the metepisternum laterally. A similar notch can also be observed in *Pachycondyla*, *Aphelotoma* and *Dolichurus*, but despite it the sclerites are fused in these terminals. Therefore, we attributed state (1) to †*Burmasphex*, †*Decasphex*, †*Callisphex* **gen.n.** and †*Simplisphex* **gen.n.**

70. Arms of meso- and meta thoracic furca:

(0) fused.

(1) not fused or only weakly fused (separate in KOH cleared specimens; Figs. 15 and 16 in Melo, 1999).

Together with loss of the interfurcal muscle, Heraty et al. (1994) considered fusion of the arms of the meso- and metathoracic furca a synapomorphy for the Apoidea. In two apoid groups, however, the arms are not immovably fused and become separated after KOH treatment. This condition was found in Ampulicidae and in the crabronid genera *Astata*, *Eremiasphexium* and *Pulverro* (as well as *Ammoplanops*). In the Ampulicidae, this probably represents a plesiomorphic condition, while in those crabronid genera, it is clearly a secondary derived condition. In the cleared specimen of *Astata nevadica*, the metafurcal arm has a cup-like expansion and the mesofurcal arm has a callus-like structure (finely fibrous) in the region where they are supposed to be fused (Fig. 15 in Melo, 1999). The lateral arm of the metafurca has also an additional cup-like expansion on its tip and it is weakly attached to the larger cup-like expansion projecting from the endophragmal (= upper meta pleural) apophysis. Dissection of a specimen of *Astata* sp. (Costa Rica) preserved in alcohol showed that the two furcal arms are firmly attached to each other and that the cup-like expansions of the metafurcal arms are covered with tendon-like material (finely fibrous and whitish). The KOH treatment probably breaks down this material, causing the separation of the furcal arms. In the cleared specimens of *Pulverro* and *Eremiasphexium sahelense*, the lateral arms of the metafurca are broad (laminar) and also separate from the mesofurcal arms (Fig. 16 in Melo, 1999). Apparently the two cup-like expansions observed in *Astata* fused together and became one large expansion entirely covering each lateral arm of the metafurca in these taxa.

This study. In *Pachycondyla*, the arms of the thoracic furca are juxtaposed; however, they are not considered fused since it is possible to see a finely fibrous tissue uniting them. This taxon received state (1).

71. Upper margin of discriminallamella (segment posterior to furcal arms):

(0) narrow, as broad as remainder of lamella.

(1) expanded, forming a horizontal lamella perpendicular to vertical portion.

This character applies only to taxa assigned state (1) for character 73.

72. Pseudophragma of second phragma:

(0) absent (Fig. 17 in Melo, 1999).

(1) present (Fig. 18 in Melo, 1999).

66. Mesepisternum and metepisternum:

(0) not fused laterally.

(1) fused laterally; suture mostly obliterated.

~~In most taxa, this fusion is restricted to the lower lateral parts of the mesepisternum and metepisternum.~~

73. Medial portion of mesometepisternal suture (between midcoxae):

(0) clearly visible (Fig. 59 in Melo, 1999).

(1) mostly obliterated (Figs. 23, 24, 60-62 in Melo, 1999).

In all Apoidea, the mesepisternum and metepisternum are fused ventrally. The morphology of this area is very complex and variable, making character delimitation difficult. Brothers and Carpenter (1993) consider loss of any sulcus between meso- and metepisterna, ventrally, as part of the Apoidea ground plan. However, in Ampulicidae and *Heterogyna*, the suture is clearly visible (the two lateral halves converge forward) and the midcoxal sockets are small and widely separated; also the mesal articulation is closer to the lateral articulation than to the body's midline. The coxal sockets are large and the suture is mostly obliterated only in the remaining apoids. The expansion of the coxal sockets was apparently accompanied by a posterior expansion of the mesokatepisternum, forming a broad flap covering the sockets medially (Fig. 23 in Melo, 1999); concomitantly, the suture is directed posteriorly (in lateral view; Fig. 24 in Melo, 1999). Brothers and Carpenter (1993) also inappropriately consider this condition as part of the Apoidea groundplan (see their Fig. 11 and state 57-2 in their Appendix IX). *Eremiasphecium* and the Ammoplanini have a somewhat distinct condition. Their metepisternum is not projected in the middle as a strong keel continuous with the mesepisternum (see Fig. 62 in Melo, 1999); there is a transverse line that looks like the mesometepisternal suture; this line does not seem to be homologous to the suture and it is probably a structure unique to these taxa. Despite these modifications, they are coded as having state (1).

This study. †*Burmasphex*, †*Callisphe* **gen.n** and †*Simplisphe* **gen.n**. exhibit a condition not observed in other Apoidea. While their mesometepisternal suture is clearly visible in ventral view, the mesal articulation of the mid coxa is exposed ventrally, and not hidden as in Ampulicidae. The presence of a visible suture also corresponds to possession of small and well-separate sockets of the mid coxae.

74. Relative position of the mesal condyle of the mid coxa (new character):

(0) condyle away from the body's midline and closer to the lateral articulation of the coxa;

(1) situated in a small projection of the posterior border of the mesepisternum;

(2) situated in a broad flap of the mesepisternum which covers the coxal sockets medially.

This study. In the terminals attributed state (0), the mesepisternum, right in front of the mid coxae, forms a vertical surface separate from its anterior portion by a carina.

75. Medial flap of mesokatepisternum and condyle of mesal midcoxal articulation:

(0) flap well developed and broadly continuous in the middle; portion containing condyle not or only slightly projecting (Fig. 23 and 60 in Melo, 1999).

(1) flap well developed, interrupted in the middle by a deep cleft; condyle close to midline of body, but not situated at apex of flap projection.

(2) flap well developed, interrupted in the middle by a deep cleft; condyle situated at apex of flap projection and close to midline of body (Fig. 61 and 62 in Melo, 1999).

(3) flap narrow, interrupted in the middle by a deep cleft; condyle situated at apex of flap projection and well separated from midline of body (Fig. 53 in Melo, 1999).

This character applies only to taxa assigned state (2) for the preceding character.

This region probably represents the fusion of the true katepisternum with the trochantin [see discussion in Gibson (1993)], since it seems more parsimonious to assume that the mesal articulation in the Hymenoptera is homologous to the trochantinal articulation of other insects, and not a new articulation.

76. Medial portion of metepisternum:

(0) narrow, forming a strong keel and narrowly fused to medial portion of mesokatepisternum (anterior portion of keel extending through vertical medial portion of mesokatepisternum) (Fig. 59-61 in Melo, 1999).

(1) narrow, forming a carina, perpendicular to vertical medial portion of mesokatepisternum (anterior portion of carina not extending through vertical medial portion of mesokatepisternum) (Fig. 62 in Melo, 1999).

(2) narrow, but not forming a strong keel or carina, narrowly fused to mesokatepisternum.

(3) wide and flat, broadly fused to mesokatepisternum (mesometepisternal suture transverse or V-shaped in ventral view) (Fig. 23 in Melo, 1999).

(4) wide and flat, broadly fused to mesokatepisternum

(mesometepisternal suture indistinct) (Fig. 53 in Melo, 1999).

This character applies only to taxa assigned state (1) for character 69.

Xenosphex is assigned (3) despite the fact that the medial portion of its metepisternum is mostly vertical.

This study. We attributed the state (3) to †*Burmasphex* and state (0) to †*Simplisphex*.

77. Mesocoxal carina 1:

(0) absent.

(1) present (Fig. 55-57 in Melo, 1999).

This carina runs from the lateral articulation obliquely across the coxa to the ventral articulation with the trochanter posteriorly (Michener 1981). In some taxa, for example *Aphilanthops* and *Philanthus*, it is present only basally, on the rest of the coxa being indicated by a rounded ridge; contrary to Alexander (1992a), I assigned state (1) to these taxa (but see next character). Michener (1981) assumed, without further argumentation, that the basal groove on the coxa of the Apoidea represents the separation of the basicoxite from the rest of the coxa (Michener's disticoxite) and that the mesocoxal carina is present only in those taxa whose basal groove has been displaced distally, i.e. taxa in which an enlargement of the "basicoxite" and a correlated reduction of the "disticoxite" occurred. Michener's terminology and homology assessments were also adopted by Johnson (1988) for the rest of Hymenoptera. The Xyelidae examined here has a distinct basal suture, certainly homologous to the basicostal suture of other insects as defined by Snodgrass (1993), delimiting a very short basicoxite. The other Hymenoptera examined have no such basicoxite and the basicostal suture seems to correspond to the region of attachment of the membrane connecting the base of the coxa to its thoracic socket. It is assumed here that a basicoxite is absent from the Apoidea and that the mesocoxal carina, therefore, does not mark the limit between the basicoxite and a disticoxite.

78. Mesocoxal carina 2:

- (0) weak, sometimes restricted to upper half or indicated only by a ridge (Fig. 55 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) well defined, more or less uniform throughout (Fig. 56 in Melo, 1999).
- (2) conspicuously enlarged, becoming a lamella toward lower half (Fig. 57 in Melo, 1999).

This character applies only to taxa assigned state (1) in the preceding character.

79. Basal part of mesocoxa:

- (0) more or less continuous with rest of coxa (Fig. 55-57 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) forming a narrow pedicel (coxa pedunculate) (Fig. 58 in Melo, 1999).

This study. Although Melo (1999) attributed state (0) to *Rhopalosoma* and *Clystopsenella*, we coded them here as having state (1). There is some variation among the terminals with pedunculate mesocoxae. *Clystopsenella* does not have a typical pedunculate coxa since it exhibits a lateral expansion. In other scolybythid wasps, *Ycaploca* for example, the coxa has both lateral and medial expansions, therefore characterizing the condition represented by state (1).

80. Number of mid tibial spurs:

- (0) two.
- (1) one.

81. Hind coxal socket:

- (0) closed by membrane only.
- (1) closed by a narrow sclerotized bridge connecting the propodeum to the metakatepisternum.
- (2) closed mostly by an enlargement of the medial portion of the metakatepisternum (Fig. 23 in Melo, 1999).

This study. Although the hind coxae are placed apart in †*Burmasphex* and †*Simplisphex*, it is not possible to clearly see this region in the specimens. Despite this difficulty, the posterior border of the metepisternum is clearly visible and there is no indication of a bridge connecting it to the posterior border of the propodeum. Therefore, we attributed state (0) to these two taxa. In *Pachycondyla* the socket of the hind coxa shows a sclerotized bridge, however it received state (0) considering that the projections of the metakatepisternum and of the propodeum are not fused.

82. Socket of mesal articulation on hindcoxa:

- (0) away from ventral surface of hindcoxa (distance to ventral surface at least one half of distance between socket of mesal articulation and condyle of lateral articulation).
- (1) on ventral surface of hindcoxa or very close to it (Fig. 27 in Melo, 1999).

83. Hind coxal carina:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present, well developed but not forming a lamella.
- (2) present, very strong, forming a lamella (Fig. 63 in Melo, 1999).

This hind coxal lamella is present in the Ammoplanini. In several taxa in this tribe, the lamella is stronger anteriorly and sometimes absent posteriorly, forming a spinelike projection.

84. Paired lobes on inner side of hind coxal apex:

- (0) subequal in size and separated by a narrow cleft.
- (1) dorsal lobe large, usually forming a spatulate process, ventral lobe small or absent (Fig. 64 in Melo, 1999).

Eremiasphecium and the Ammoplanini are assigned state (1) despite the fact that their coxal apices are practically straight, without any lobes (see Fig. 63 in Melo, 1999). In *Ochleroptera*, the lobes are subequal in size, but the dorsal one is spatulate; it is assigned state (1). In *Heterogyna*, *Clystopsenella* and *Sierolomorpha*, the lobes are very small and separated by a shallow notch in the female and practically nil in the male; these taxa are assigned state (0).

85. Dorsal apical process on inner surface of hindcoxa:

- (0) relatively small, trochanter without any conspicuous depression.
- (1) well developed, articulating with a basal depression on inner surface of trochanter, apical edge of depression not delimited by a weak crest (Fig. 64 in Melo, 1999).
- (2) as (1) or even more developed, apical edge of trochanterical depression delimited by a weak crest.
- (3) nil (Fig. 63 in Melo, 1999).

This character applies only for taxa assigned state (1) in the preceding character.

These modifications of the coxa and trochanter are probably related to the truncation of the femoral apex, since they are more developed in taxa with such modified femora (see next character), like *Entomosericus* and *Odontosphex* (also *Bothynostethus*, *Cerceris*, *Oxybelus* and a few other crabronid taxa). These structures probably allow the femur to be locked in one position.

86. Apex of hind femur (females):

- (0) unmodified.
- (1) broadened, truncate.
- (2) with an apical spatulate process.

87. Basitibial plate (females):

- (0) absent.
- (1) present.

88. Hind tibial bristles:

- (0) present (at least one).
- (1) absent.

These bristles correspond to relatively large and spiniform setae, in contrast to the fine and usually shorter setae also present on the hind tibia. Despite the large and plumose setae on the hind tibia of bees, bristles are considered absent from these taxa; their plumose setae probably correspond only to enlarged fine setae.

89. Gland on posterior surface of hind tibia:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present (Figs. 65-67 in Melo, 1999).

The presence of this gland was initially inferred from the distinct micropore field [term taken from Finnamore (1995)] on the posterior surface of the tibia (Figs. 65 and 66 in Melo, 1999). Its presence was confirmed with histological sectioning only for *Ammoplanus* (Fig. 67). This gland

possibly is absent from *Timberlakena*, because there is no micropore field on its hind tibia, except for a transverse darker area in the region where the field is situated in the other Ammoplanini. It is assigned (?), because a histological study might reveal the presence of the gland.

90. Pterostigma:

(0) flat, not conspicuously thickened.

(1) thickened dorso-ventrally (Figs. 72-74 in Melo, 1999), in dry specimens postero-medial portion conspicuously convex ventrally.

A thickened pterostigma is present in members of the subtribes Pemphredonina and Stigmina of the Pemphredonini. In *Stigmus*, the pterostigma is greatly enlarged and both dorsal and ventral surfaces possess a distinct micropore field (Figs. 68-71 in Melo, 1999); under these fields, there is a thick glandular epidermis (Figs. 72 and 73 in Melo, 1999). This gland is probably present in all Stigmina, because most of them also have a distinct micropore field on the pterostigma. Also a somewhat diffuse micropore field is present in *Diodontus* (Fig. 75 in Melo, 1999). The pterostigma of *Passaloecus* is similarly swollen, but no glandular tissue was detected (Fig. 74 in Melo, 1999).

91. Width of forewing costal cell:

(0) at least as wide as width of vein C.

(1) linear, narrower than vein C.

Maximum width measured perpendicular to costal margin of wing. *Dinetus* was assigned state (0), but its condition is somewhat intermediate between the two states. *Laphyragogus* is assigned (?) because its vein C is unusually slender.

92. Pterostigma width:

(0) less than or subequal to length of prestigma (Sc + R distal to Rs).

(1) at least one and a third the length of prestigma.

Maximum width measured perpendicular to costal wing margin.

93. Marginal cell:

(0) longer than pterostigma (measured along vein C) (Fig. 19 in Melo, 1999).

(1) shorter than pterostigma (Figs. 20-22 in Melo, 1999).

Some species of *Astata* have a marginal cell longer than the pterostigma, but the remaining Astatini have state (1), including *A. nevadica*. Considering that *Astata* does not seem to be the most basal lineage within the tribe, the relatively long marginal cell in some of its species might represent a derived condition. A positive correlation between body size and relative length of the wing cells has been documented for the Hymenoptera (Danforth 1989). Since *Astata* contains the largest forms in the tribe, it is expected that they have longer cells as well.

94. Segment of Rs separating 1st and 2nd submarginal cells:

(0) present.

(1) absent.

The characters of forewing venation for *Eremiasphecium* were taken from *E. longiceps* and not from *E. sahelense*, because this latter species has some reductions that are probably not part of the ground plan for the genus [see also Fig. 184G in Bohart and Menke (1976) for the wing

venation of *E. schmiedeknechtii* Kohl]. For *Heterogyna*, wing characters taken from male of *H. protea*.

95. Forewing 2rs-m:

- (0) present.
- (1) absent.

Present only as nebulous vein in *Heterogyna*.

96. Forewing M (distal to 2rs-m) and 3rs-m:

- (0) present.
- (1) absent.

Present only as spectral veins in *Sierolomorpha*.

This study. Although part of the vein M is present in *Pachycondyla*, we attributed state (1) to it.

97. Forewing CuA1 and 2m-cu:

- (0) present.
- (1) absent (discal cell2 absent).

Present only as spectral veins in *Sierolomorpha*.

98. Forewing Rs (anterior to 2r-rs) and 2rs-m:

- (0) separated by Rs (segment distal to 2r-rs) anteriorly (Fig. 19 and 21 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) touching anteriorly (i.e., 2nd submarginal cell pointed anteriorly).
- (2) fused anteriorly (i.e., 2nd submarginal cell petiolate; Figs. 20 and 22 in Melo, 1999).

Nitela, *Lindenius* and *Anacrabro* are assigned (?) for this character because some of the veins involved are absent, but there is good evidence that their reduced venation pattern is derived from lineages with a petiolate 2nd submarginal cell.

99. Forewing M and CuA:

- (0) diverging distal to cu-a.
- (1) diverging at cu-a.
- (2) diverging basal to cu-a.

100. Forewing M + CuA (distal to cu-a):

- (0) subequal to or shorter than cu-a (Fig. 21 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) longer than cu-a (Fig. 19 and 20 in Melo, 1999).

This character applies only to taxa assigned states (0) or (1) in the preceding character.

101. Forewing M (basal to Rs):

- (0) gently curved or straight (Figs. 19,20 and 22 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) strongly bent (Fig. 21 in Melo, 1999).

102. Forewing vein CuA2:

- (0) present, reaching vein 1A.
- (1) much reduced or absent, not reaching vein 1A.

103. Hindwing C:

- (0) present.
- (1) absent.

In *Heterogyna*, *Epyris* and *Clystopsenella*, it is not possible to determine if the vein along the costal margin of the hindwing represents only Sc+R or a fusion of C with Sc+R. They are assigned(?).

104. Hind wing M:

- (0) diverging from CuA before or at cu-a (Fig. 19 in Melo, 1999).
- (1) diverging from CuA after cu-a.

Nitela and *Timberlakena* are assigned (?) because their hind wing venation is very reduced and parts of the veins involved are lacking.

105. Hind wing vein 2A:

- (0) indicated at least as a short spur on basal portion of 1A.
- (1) absent.

106. Hind wing clavus (= plical lobe):

- (0) indicated posterodistally by moderate incision.
- (1) indicated by short incision or only a shallow notch.
- (2) not indicated posterodistally on wing margin.

107. Jugal lobe:

- (0) absent.
- (1) small to moderately long and indicated by distinct incision.
- (2) large and not indicated by an incision on wing margin (fused to clavus).

108. Metapostnotum I:

- (0) transverse, depressed and distinct mesally between metanotum and propodeum (or shortened).
- (1) strongly expanded posteromesally to form "propodeal triangle".

This study. Despite lack of a clear indication of an expanded metapostnotum in †*Burmasphex*, †*Decasphe*, †*Callisphe* **gen.n.**, and †*Simplisphe* **gen.n.**, we attributed state (1) to them considering the external morphology of their propodeal region, which exhibits a large dorsal surface. The dorsal surface is about as long as the posterior surface of the propodeum, giving a box-like appearance to the entire propodeum which is characteristic of the basal apoid wasps. In †*Burmasphex*, there is a strong transverse carina separating the dorsal and posterior surfaces and that prolongs downward at the lateral portions of the propodeum. The dorsal surface is also limited laterally by a carina extending at each side from behind the spiracle and that connects posteriorly to the transverse carina. Lack of indication of the limits of the metapostnotum is observed also in extant Ampulicidae and in *Heterogyna*. We considered that †*Angarosphex* also possessed an expanded metapostnotum, as found in all Apoidea. Melo (1999) assumed that *Chlorepyris* (cited as *Epyris*), in the outgroup, did not have an expanded metapostnotum, but more recently Kawada et al. (2015) demonstrated that the metapostnotum is expanded posteriorly in Bethylidae. We maintained here the state (0) for *Chlorepyris*, since the condition in the Bethylidae is distinct from that of the Apoidea.

109. Metapostnotum II (propodeal enclosure):

- (0) restricted to dorsal surface of propodeum, apex rounded.
- (1) extending as a narrow triangle into posterior surface of propodeum, but for less than half the length of the posterior surface.
- (2) extending as a narrow triangle for more than half the length of the posterior surface, but not reaching posterior apex of propodeum.
- (3) extending as a narrow triangle to posterior apex of propodeum.

This character applies only to taxa assigned state (1) in the preceding character.

It is being used to represent an apparent progressive shortening of the propodeum and a simultaneous relative elongation and posterior narrowing of the metapostnotum within Apoidea.

This study. We considered that the expanded metapostnotum in †*Angarosphex*, †*Burmasphex*, †*Decasphex*, †*Callisphex* **gen.n.** and †*Simplisphex* **gen.n.**, is restricted to the dorsal portion of the propodeal region and coded them as (0). The posterior surface of their propodeum is quite flat and shows no indication of being divided by an extension of the metapostnotum.

110. General sculpture of the propodeum and metapostnotum (new character):

- (0) surface mostly smooth, or at most with some fine carinae forming an irregular pattern or striations;
- (1) surface with strong and high carinae forming an anastomosing areolate pattern.

This study. We are using this character to represent the characteristic sculpture observed in the propodeum of Ampulicidae. Some groups of Crabronidae (mostly in Bembicinae, Crabroninae and Pemphredoninae) also exhibit a similar pattern. Terminals from these groups included here were coded as (1). Other groups of crabronid wasps have strong carinae along the posterior edges of the propodeum, but they do not form an areolate pattern. These were coded as (0).

111. Third mesosomal phragma:

- (0) forming a transverse, vertical flange, continuous or narrowly interrupted in the middle.
- (1) forming only a narrow medial, transverse flap, situated at the apex of expanded metapostnotum.
- (2) as (1), but flap longitudinal.
- (3) as (1), but forming a spine-like projection.
- (4) absent or indistinctly fused to metapostnotum (except sometimes for presence of a longitudinal carina).

This study. Although not explicitly stated by Melo (1999), this character is also contingent on state (1) of character 108.

112. Triangular posterior extension of metapostnotum:

- (0) flat or forming a broad, shallow sulcus.
- (1) forming a narrow, deep sulcus (Fig. 76 in Melo, 1999).

This character applies only to taxa assigned states (1) to (3) for character 109.

Metasoma.**113. Metasomal petiole:**

~~(0) absent, tergum I and sternum I not immovably fused, suture between them clearly visible.~~

~~(1) present, tergum I and sternum I fused anteriorly, portion of tergum I forming petiole very reduced, suture between tergum I and sternum I along petiole mostly obliterated.~~

~~(2) present, tergum I and sternum I not fused, sclerites subequal in size, suture between them clearly visible.~~

(0) suture between tergum I and sternum I clearly visible along entire length of sclerites, metasomal segment I forming or not a petiole;

(1) basal portion of segment I forming a tubular petiole, of variable length, with the suture between tergum and sternum completely obliterated along the petiole.

Dolichurus has what looks like a very short petiole and is coded as state (1).

This study. Here we simplified the states used by Melo (1999) to represent only the degree of fusion between the metasomal tergum I and sternum I irrespective of the shape of segment I (either elongated or not). In Melo (1999), *Rhopalosoma* was erroneously attributed state (3), while the correct option would have been state (2). Here this taxon received state (0). Considering the highly modified condition of the metasomal segments I and II of *Pachycondyla*, characters 113–118 were based instead on the male of *Fulakora*.

114. Lateral line on tergum I:

(0) present, sometimes marked as a weak carina.

(1) absent.

115. Lateral carina on base of tergum I (dorsal to lateral line):

(0) absent.

(1) present, basal portion simple.

(2) present, basal portion protuberant.

116. Medial longitudinal ridge on base of sternum I:

(0) absent.

(1) present, more developed basally.

This study. There is a medial longitudinal carina on the disc of sternum I of †*Burmasphex*. However, it does not extend to the base of the sternum and therefore we attributed state (0) to this terminal.

117. Second sternum posteromedially:

(0) slightly convex to flat, basal portion more or less at same level as remainder of sclerite.

(1) strongly convex, basal portion distinctly in a different level in relation to remainder of sclerite, surface separating these two portions almost vertical (Fig. 28 in Melo, 1999).

This character is used to recognize the distinct condition found in the Ampulicidae. *Palarus* and males of *Heliocausus* have sternum II modified (with transverse and thick keels), but differently from the condition found in the Ampulicidae. These two taxa are assigned state (0) to avoid creating autapomorphic states for them.

This study. †*Burmasphex* exhibits a marked constriction between metasomal segments I and II, which involves both the terga and sterna. Its sternum II is strongly convex, with the basal portion in a distinct level compared to remainder of sclerite. The condition is reminiscent of that exhibited

by the Ampulicidae, but in the latter the surfaces are separated by a strong, almost vertical step, while in †*Burmasphex* the sternum II possesses a gentle curvature connecting its basal portion to the sclerite disc.

118. Basal portion of lateral gradulus of sternum II.

- (0) simple, not modified, or gradulus absent.
- (1) laminar and directed inward, forming a specialized articulating surface with the differentiated posterior portion of the lateral edge of sternum I (Fig. 77 in Melo, 1999).

119. Anterior lateral epidermal gland on sternum II:

- (0) situated mesal to lateral gradulus.
- (1) situated lateral to lateral gradulus (Fig. in Melo, 1999).

Taxa in which the lateral gradulus is absent, as well as those in which the gland could not be detected, were coded as (?).

120. Adult female silk glands:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present, associated with tergum VI.
- (2) present, associated with sterna IV and V.

See Melo (1997) for more details on the structure, function and taxonomic distribution of these glands.

121. Female pygidial plate (tergum VI):

- (0) absent.
- (1) present.

122. Sixth metasomal sternum (females):

- (0) similar to other segments, except for troughlike vertical side walls.
- (1) elongate, forming an exposed tapering tube through which sting is exerted.

123. Apex of female sternum VI medially:

- (0) simple (truncate, slightly rounded or emarginate), more or less continuous with lateral portions of the apex.
- (1) forming a medial lobe (Fig. 79 in Melo, 1999).
- (2) with two pointed projections separated by a deep V-emargination (Fig. 80 in Melo, 1999).
- (3) denticulate (Fig. 81 in Melo, 1999).

124. Seventh metasomal tergum of female I:

- (0) partly exposed and evenly sclerotized.
- (1) hidden under tergum VI and considerably desclerotized.

125. Seventh metasomal tergum of female II:

- (0) two broad, lateral plates connected anteriorly by a sclerotized bridge.
- (1) as (0), but bridge displaced toward posterior margin of tergum.
- (2) lateral plates narrow (not sclerotized dorsad to spiracles), connected by a narrow, but strongly sclerotized bridge.
- (3) as (2), but lateral segments of bridge forming a 90° angle with dorsal segment.

(4) forming two separate lateral plates (hemitergites), connected by membrane only.

This character applies only to taxa assigned state (1) in the preceding character.

126. Female hemitergites VIII:

(0) narrowly connected dorsally by a sclerotized bridge.

(1) connected by membrane only.

127. Female gonapophyses VIII in lateral view:

(0) strongly curving downward.

(1) gently curving downward.

(2) straight.

(3) curving upward.

Ctenocolletes is assigned (?) because its sting is very reduced (gonapophyses widely separated at their bases).

128. Articulation within gonocoxite IX of female:

(0) absent.

(1) present.

129. Male tergum VII:

(0) entire.

(1) with lateral lobes.

130. Male cerci (tergum VIII):

(0) present.

(1) absent.

131. Male sternum VII:

(0) partly exposed.

(1) completely hidden under sternum VI.

132. Apex of male sternum VIII:

(0) continuous with disk or forming a broad and short medial lobe (broader than or as broad as long).

(1) forming a medial lobe or projection longer than broad, but less than 3x longer than wide, relatively broad.

(2) medial projection more than 3x longer than wide, broad, sides diverging distally.

(3) as (2), but narrow and sides parallel or converging distally.

(4) with two long, lateral spiniform projections.

(5) forming three long, spiniform projections.

133. Lateral margin of projection of male sternum VIII:

(0) entire.

(1) serrate (Fig. 82 in Melo, 1999).

(2) with short, thick bristles.

134. Apical margin of male sternum VIII:

- (0) entire.
- (1) denticulate.

135. Posterior edge of gonobase foramen (ventrally):

- (0) close to bases of gonocoxites.
- (1) widely separated from bases of gonocoxites.

136. Volsellae:

- (0) clearly differentiated from gonocoxites.
- (1) largely fused to gonocoxites, usually small or sometimes apparently absent.

137. Gonapophyses of male genitalia dorsally:

- (0) connected by membrane only or by a sclerotized bridge, but not forming a distinct tube.
- (1) completely fused, forming a tube.

Various forms of sclerotized bridges are found among the taxa analyzed, making difficult the recognition of discrete states. This character is used to recognize the distinct condition found among several Crabroninae.

138. Apicoventral edge of gonapophyses of male genitalia:

- (0) without teeth.
- (1) with numerous short teeth.

Sometimes, these teeth are very inconspicuous, like those in *Mellinus* [see illustrations in Menke (1996)].

Larvae.

139. Larval integument:

- (0) with minute spicules or smooth.
- (1) with dense, short spicules.
- (2) with dense, conspicuous seta-like acanthae.

In the descriptions of the larva of *Mimesa bicolor*, Janvier (1956) makes no reference to the integument; *Mimesa* was coded as (?).

140. Position of larval anus:

- (0) terminal, directed caudad.
- (1) ventral, preapical, directed ventrad.

141. Larval antennal papillae:

- (0) absent (sometimes the orbits are protuberant, but there are no papillae).
- (1) present, usually well developed and conspicuous.

142. Larval maxillae:

- (0) directed mesad apically, closely associated with labium and hypopharynx.

(1) projecting apically as large, free lobes.

143. Larval galea:

- (0) large, subequal in size to maxillary palpus.
- (1) small, less than half the size of maxillary palpus.
- (2) absent.

144. Larval spinneret:

- (0) a transverse slit.
- (1) with paired openings, each at the end of a projection.
- (2) absent.

Biology.

145. Provisions for larvae:

- (0) Orthopteroids (Blattodea, Mantodea, Phasmatodea and Orthoptera).
- (1) Thysanoptera.
- (2) Hemiptera (Heteroptera and Auchenorrhyncha)
- (3) immature Holometabola.
- (4) adult Holometabola.
- (5) pollen.
- (6) Araneae.

Besides preying on aphids, *Nitela* is also known to prey on Psocoptera, but this state was not included because, among the exemplar taxa, it would be present only in this genus. *Lindenius* and *Arpactophilus* are assigned more than one state. *Nysson* and *Eusapyga* are coded (?) since they are cleptoparasites.

146. Relocation of larval food:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present.

Chlorion is assigned both states. *Epyris* females are known to relocate their prey, but this is an exception for bethylids; it is assigned (0).

147. Construction of a nest before obtaining larval food:

- (0) absent.
- (1) present.

Chlorion and *Podalonia* are assigned both states.

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